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**Title: Patterns of Environmentally Sustainable Practices and their impact on Export
Competitiveness: An Indian Outlook**

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Patterns of Environmentally Sustainable Practices and their impact on Export Competitiveness: An Indian Outlook

Extended Abstract

Introduction

India, an emerging innovation-based country, has several factor advantages. Rising exports in innovative, export-oriented industries, such as IT (Haldar et al., 2016), in the early part of the 21st century and the scope for them to accelerate and scale up (Manthri et al., 2015), are encouraging trends. However, the upward journey in the country's competitiveness ranks (Momaya, 2015), seems to be driven largely by demand factors. Samples such as Fortune Global 500 show that the number of firms of Indian origin (FIOs) had stagnated at eight during 2008-13 (Momaya, 2014). A similar trend continues till date, with only seven appearing in the list for the year 2019 (Fortune Global 500, 2019). Stagnation in India's exports (particularly to developed countries), coupled with India's inability to balance international trade even after sixty years of independence (Momaya, 2014) indicate massive gaps in business competitiveness. A break-out is therefore needed to enable FIOs to climb the stairs of international competitiveness (Momaya, 2001). A push towards the newer frontiers of environmental sustainability promises to provide the FIOs the momentum to break-out from the traps of the factor-driven stage to the higher stages on the ladder of international competitiveness (Momaya, 2014).

Key objective and sub-objective

The key objective of this paper is to analyse the patterns of incorporation of environmentally sustainable practices (ESPs) among FIOs and their impact on the export competitiveness and profitability. The primary sub-objective of the paper is to identification of industries in which the relationship between incorporation of ESPs and boost to export competitiveness hold better than the rest.

The research questions that this study seeks to find answers to include:

- Does incorporation of ESPs contribute significantly to export competitiveness?
- Are there clearly identifiable relationships between incorporation of ESPs and the trends in profitability of FIOs belonging to select high potential industries?
- Do some moderating variables (for example, proxies for innovation, effective management of technology etc.) influence the journey of export competitiveness or profitability?

Literature Review

We explored two key streams of literature for review—ESPs and Export Competitiveness to understand any gaps in the existing body of knowledge. This brief literature review touches upon the key takeaways from the same.

ESPs

Jose and Saraf (2013), after carefully shortlisting and classifying the top 100 private sector companies (as per BT 500) into 15 sectors, explored the disclosure of sustainability initiatives and found that of late, there is a heightened emphasis on the management of environment and greening of operations. Placing greater emphasis on sustainability practices has been confirmed to show better financial performance in many crucial aspects of businesses, including return on assets, profit before taxation and cash flow from operations (Ameer et al., 2012).

Export Competitiveness

The software industry, banking on its export competitiveness, has attracted attention of the masses as well as researchers by creating massive job opportunities for the technically skilled youth in India. Umamaheswari et al., (2008) however found vast opportunities for FIOs to climb up on the value curve. They also proposed an approach to define and measures to identify ‘breakthrough growth firms’ (Umamaheswari et al., 2011) which can open up opportunities for the technically skilled youth. Bhawsar and Chattopadhyay (2015) did an extensive review of competitiveness literature to explore new directions. Manthri et al., (2015) explored patterns of export competitiveness for firms in several industries using the simple concept of trade competitiveness index (TCI). Haldar et al., (2016) explored linkages between corporate governance (CG) and export competitiveness taking the comparative case of two R&D intensive export-driven industries of India—pharmaceuticals and software. Importance of flexibility in CG and size was confirmed for scale-up in export competitiveness.

The existing literature, to the best of our knowledge, does not however sufficiently bridge the gap in our understanding of the linkage between export competitiveness/profitability and sustainability. This is the area in which this study proposes to add unique value.

Methodology

This paper is based on the findings of the first phase of a two-phase exploratory research project. The first phase focuses more on qualitative analysis of secondary data collected from multiple sources—literature, databases and other archival data. The second phase will involve a more detailed analysis of the data using relevant statistical tools. We also plan to explore comparative multiple case analysis of carefully selected firms for confirmatory analysis.

Keeping in mind the broad objective, industries with high export intensities and profitability which have adequate scope for both incorporating ESPs and improving export competitiveness, were selected from among the top 20 industries (according to Capitaline Databases) in the first phase. Large Computer Software, Pharmaceuticals, Engineering Turnkey and Paints emerged to be high potential industries above average cut-off of net profits as percentage of sales of 4.35%. Refineries and Petrochemicals is another industry with huge export potential which can help India achieve balances on international trade. Engineering goods and services (e.g. 2W, 3W and small cars) is yet another industry with high job opportunities, if exports can be scaled-up.

Expected results

An overall trend of heightened focus on ESPs is expected. It is also expected that there will be a positive correlation between the incorporation of ESPs and export competitiveness. This would imply that such practices generally tend to boost competitiveness. Among the select high potential industries, Large Computer Software and Pharmaceuticals may emerge to have stronger linkages of ESPs with profitability.

The results highlighted herein are indicative and not final. This study is an ongoing one and final results may see deviations from the ones expected.

Implications

A positive correlation between specific ESPs and exports, if proven, may ease decision-making for investment in those ESPs. As several emerging MNE FIOs get ready for break-out in international competitiveness (Momaya, 2014, 2015), sharper understanding about

ESPs may help them invest in more relevant innovations and would facilitate better management of technology and innovation (MoT) for export competitiveness.

Unique Value Added

Our study proposes to provide a new perspective of MoT and sustainability on the vexing problem of 'stagnation in export competitiveness for FIOs'. To the best of our knowledge, this is a unique topic with high relevance for leaders in industry, academia and policy. Identification of industries and firms in next phase of study can help intensify efforts by leaders in those companies to climb higher levels of export competitiveness through MoT.

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